

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 27

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 27

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 27:1 The LORD is my ^alight and my ^bsalvation; Whom shall I fear? The LORD is the ^{1c}defense of my life; ^dWhom shall I dread? ² When evildoers came upon me to ^adevour my flesh, My adversaries and my enemies, they ^bstumbled and fell. ³ Though a ^ahost encamp against me, My heart will not fear; Though war arise against me, In <i>spite of</i> this I ¹shall be ^bconfident.</p>	<p>Psa. 27:1 וַיִּשְׁעֵי מִמִּי אֵירָא יְהוָה מִמִּי אֶפְחָד : ² בְּקָרֵב עָלַי וּמְרַעִים לֹא אֲכַל אֶת-בְּשָׂרִי צָרִי וְאֹיְבֵי לִי הִמָּה כָּשְׁלוּ וְנָפְלוּ : ³ אִם- תַּחֲנֶה עָלַי וּמִחֲנֶה לֹא-יִירָא לִבִּי אִם-תִּקְוֶם עָלַי מִלְחָמָה בְּזֹאת אֲנִי בּוֹטֵחַ : ⁴ אַתָּה </p>
<p>Psa. 27:4 ^aOne thing I have asked from the LORD, that I shall seek: That I may ^bdwell in the house of the LORD all the days of my life, To behold ^athe ¹beauty of the LORD And to ^{2d}meditate in His temple. ⁵ For in the ^aday of trouble He will ^bconceal me in His ¹tabernacle; In the secret place of His tent He will ^ahide me; He will ^alift me up on a rock. ⁶ And now ^amy head will be lifted up above my enemies around me, And I will offer in His tent ^bsacrifices ¹with shouts of joy; I will ^asing, yes, I will sing praises to the LORD.</p>	<p>שְׁאַלְתִּי מֵאֵת-יְהוָה אוֹתָהּ אֲבַקֵּשׁ שְׁבֵתִי בְּבֵית-יְהוָה כָּל-יְמֵי תַיִי לַחֲזוֹת בְּנֹעַם- יְהוָה וּלְבַקֵּר בְּהֵיכָלֹ : ⁵ כִּי יִצְפֶּנִּי וּבְסֹכֶה בְּיוֹם רָעָה יִסְתַּרְנִי בְּסֵתֶר אֹהֶלוֹ בְּצֹר יְרוּמֶנִי : ⁶ וְעָתָה יְרוּם רֹאשִׁי עַל אֹיְבֵי סְבִיבוֹתַי וְאֶזְבְּחָהּ בְּאֹהֶלוֹ זִבְחֵי תְרוּעָה אֲשִׁירָה וְאֶזְמְרָה לַיהוָה : ⁷ שְׁמַע-יְהוָה קוֹלִי</p>

Psa. 27:7 ^aHear, O LORD, when I cry with my voice,

And be gracious to me and ^banswer me.

⁸ *When You said, "Seek My face,"* my heart said to You,

"Your face, O LORD, ^bI shall seek."

⁹ *Do not hide Your face from me,* Do not turn Your servant away in

^banger;

You have been ^cmy help;

^dDo not abandon me nor ^eforsake me,

O God of my salvation!

¹⁰ *For my father and ^amy mother* have forsaken me,

But ^bthe LORD will take me up.

Psa. 27:11 ^aTeach me Your way, O LORD,

And lead me in a ^blevel path Because of ¹my foes.

¹² Do not deliver me over to the ^{1a}desire of my adversaries,

For ^bfalse witnesses have risen against me,

And such as ^cbreathe out violence.

¹³ *I would have despaired* unless I had believed that I would see the ^agoodness of the LORD

In the ^bland of the living.

¹⁴ ^aWait for the LORD;

Be ^bstrong and let your heart take courage;

Yes, wait for the LORD.

אֶקְרָא וְתַגִּבֵנִי וְעֲנֵנִי : 8 לְךָ |

אָמַר לִבִּי בִקְשׁוּ פָנַי אֶת-

פָּנֶיךָ יְהוָה אֲבַקֵּשׁ : 9 אֶל-

תִּסְתֵּר פָּנֶיךָ אִמְנֵנִי אֶל-

תִּטְּ-בְּאַף עֲבֹדְךָ עֲזַרְתִּי

הָיִיתָ אֶל-תִּטְּשֵׁנִי וְאֶל-

תִּעֲזֹבֵנִי אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל : 10 כִּי-

אָבִי וְאִמִּי עֲזָבוּנִי וַיְהוָה

יִאֲסֹפֵנִי : 11 תּוֹרֵנִי יְהוָה

וְדַרְכְּךָ וְנִתַּנִּי בְּאַרְחַת מִישׁוֹר

לְמַעַן שׁוֹרְרֵי : 12 אֶל-תִּתַּנֵּנִי

בְּנַפְשׁ צָרִי כִּי קָמוּ-בִי עֲדֵי-

שָׁקֵר וַיִּבַּח תְּחָמָס : 13 לוֹלֵא

הָאֲמֵנֹתַי לְרְאוֹת בְּטוֹב-יְהוָה

בְּאַרְצָתַי תִּיָּם : 14 קִנְיָה אֶל-

יְהוָה תִּזְק וַיִּאֲמַץ לִבִּי וְקִנְיָה

אֶל-יְהוָה :

References

<p>Psalm 27:1 ¹Or <i>refuge</i> ^aPs 18:28; Is 60:20; Mic 7:8 ^bEx 15:2; Ps 62:7; 118:14; Is 33:2; Jon 2:9 ^cPs 28:8 ^dPs 118:6</p> <p>Psalm 27:2 ^aPs 14:4 ^bPs 9:3</p> <p>Psalm 27:3 ¹Lit <i>am confident</i> ^aPs 3:6 ^bJob 4:6</p> <p>Psalm 27:4 ¹Lit <i>delightfulness</i> ²Lit <i>inquire</i> ^aPs 26:8 ^bPs 23:6 ^cPs 90:17 ^dPs 18:6</p> <p>Psalm 27:5 ¹Or <i>shelter</i> ^aPs 50:15 ^bPs 31:20 ^cPs 17:8 ^dPs 40:2</p> <p>Psalm 27:6 ¹Lit <i>of shouts</i> ^aPs 3:3 ^bPs 107:22 ^cPs 13:6</p> <p>Psalm 27:7</p>	<p>Psalm 27:7 ^aPs 4:3; 61:1 ^bPs 13:3</p> <p>Psalm 27:8 ^aPs 105:4; Amos 5:6 ^bPs 34:4</p> <p>Psalm 27:9 ^aPs 69:17 ^bPs 6:1 ^cPs 40:17 ^dPs 94:14 ^ePs 37:28</p> <p>Psalm 27:10 ¹Or <i>If my father...forsake me, Then the LORD</i> ^aIs 49:15 ^bIs 40:11</p> <p>Psalm 27:11 ¹Or <i>those who lie in wait for me</i> ^aPs 25:4; 86:11 ^bPs 5:8; 26:12</p> <p>Psalm 27:12 ¹Lit <i>soul</i> ^aPs 41:2 ^bDeut 19:18; Ps 35:11; Matt 26:60 ^cActs 9:1</p> <p>Psalm 27:13 ¹Or <i>Surely I believed</i> ^aPs 31:19 ^bJob 28:13; Ps 52:5; 116:9; 142:5; Is 38:11; Jer 11:19; Ezek 26:20</p>
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^aPs 4:3; 61:1

^bPs 13:3

Psalm 27:8

^aPs 105:4; Amos 5:6

^bPs 34:4

Psalm 27:9

^aPs 69:17

^bPs 6:1

^cPs 40:17

^dPs 94:14

^ePs 37:28

Psalm 27:10

¹*Or If my father...forsake me, Then the LORD*

^aIs 49:15

^bIs 40:11

Psalm 27:11

¹*Or those who lie in wait for me*

^aPs 25:4; 86:11

^bPs 5:8; 26:12

Psalm 27:12

¹*Lit soul*

^aPs 41:2

^bDeut 19:18; Ps 35:11; Matt 26:60

^cActs 9:1

Psalm 27:13

¹*Or Surely I believed*

^aPs 31:19

^bJob 28:13; Ps 52:5; 116:9; 142:5; Is 38:11;

Jer 11:19; Ezek 26:20

Psalm 27:14

^aPs 25:3; 37:34; 40:1; 62:5; 130:5; Prov 20:22; Is 25:9

^bPs 31:24

Targum

27:1 Of David. The LORD is my light and my redemption; whom shall I fear? The LORD is the strength of my life; whom shall I fear? ² Whenever evildoers come near to me to destroy my flesh, my oppressors and my foes – they have stumbled and fallen. ³ If an army of the wicked encamps against me, my heart will not fear; if battle rises against me, in this I place my hope. ⁴ One thing I have sought from the presence of the LORD; that thing I will continue to seek: that I should dwell in the sanctuary of the LORD all the days of my life, to see the pleasantness of the LORD and to inquire in his temple. ⁵ For he will hide me in his shadow in the day of evil, he will conceal me in the hiding place of his tabernacle, in a mighty fortress he will raise me up. ⁶ And now my head will be lifted up over my enemies round about; and I will slaughter acceptable sacrifices in his tabernacle; I will sing praise and be glad in the presence of the LORD. ⁷ Receive, O LORD, my prayer when I call, and have mercy on me and pity me. ⁸ To you my heart said, "Seek my face"; your countenance, O LORD, I will seek. ⁹ Do not remove your presence from me; do not turn in anger to your servant; you have been my help; do not exile me and do not abandon me, O God my redemption. ¹⁰ Because my father (abba) and my mother have abandoned me, but the LORD will gather me in. ¹¹ Teach me, O LORD, your ways, and lead me by a straight path because of my Psalm. ¹² Do not hand me over to the will of my oppressors, for the false witnesses have risen against me, and those who speak rapacity. ¹³ Had I not believed I would look on the goodness of the LORD in the land of eternal life! ¹⁴ Hope in the LORD; strengthen and fortify your heart; and hope in the LORD. --

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite would be so close to the current English translation that it was not done.

Introduction

This Psalm is used today during the "Days of Awe" in the month of Elul. It is recited on the festival of Succot by many Jews. The Psalm has nothing to do with repentance. However, it does teach us how to live without sin. A person who is fully engrossed in a single-minded dedication to the LORD has no room for sin. The Psalm expresses the thoughts and attitudes which filled David's spirit and guided him in his life on earth.

Verse one

David acknowledged that the LORD's greatness and might are so overwhelming that he felt tiny before him. David felt no fear because he knew that the LORD would not allow him to perish at the hands of men who did not believe in Him.

Verse two

רִי וְאֹיְבֵי לִי (ra v'oy'va lee)- means "adversaries and enemies to." This phrase is a parenthetical expression meaning "I saw in them, my enemies." David saw certain persons as his enemy. However, the LORD views them as evildoers because they want to kill the LORD's anointed King.

Verse three

מַחֲנֵה (machaney) – means "enemy." This word is in the feminine gender in this sentence. Therefore, it shows that David deemed that this enemy that he spoke of could not harm him because he was stronger than them.

Verse four

To dwell in the house of the LORD all the days of my life does not mean that David wanted to spend every minute of his life in the Temple. Since the Temple in Jerusalem was not built yet, this phrase must have a different meaning. It describes the conception of life and the fulfillment of its duties set by the LORD, making any place a Divine sanctuary for the Shekinah. Any place can be transformed into a Temple for LORD.

Verse five

David knew that the LORD sheltered him from trouble. In this case, it was the enemies that he had. David took the throne of Israel by force. Samuel anointed him to become the King of Israel. However, when Saul and Jonathan died, other sons took the throne. A minor civil disturbance developed, and David and his army had to defeat the sons of Saul. Even when the fighting stopped, men loyal to Saul's house tried to remove David.

Verse six

While his enemies surrounded David, the LORD's presence was with him through his awareness of the Shekinah. He knew that he would survive any attack because the LORD anointed him to be the King of Israel. The LORD's Will must be followed. That helped David's concern of being murdered by Saul's followers.

Verse seven

This verse is interesting because since David expressed that he was sure that the LORD was with him, he still calls out for Divine grace to fall upon him. David asks for an answer to his calling, but he has it already. When looking at the remainder of the Psalm, David is asking for everything he just acknowledged that he had.

Verse eight

The LORD gave a Divine order to seek him. Humans cannot look upon the face of the LORD because death would occur. The LORD told Moses this when he was on Mount Sinai. Therefore, to search for the face of the LORD is to seek out the Shekinah so that the love and grace of the LORD can be felt.

Verse nine

David beseeches the LORD to make himself known to him.

Verse ten

Parental love is one of the most vital forms of love. For a child, only the love of the LORD is stronger. David knew that even if his parents stopped loving him that the LORD would never stop.

Verse eleven

David referred to his morality. He wanted to remain ethical in the face of enemies. In wartime, there are few rules. It is easy to break the laws of the LORD when faced with death. David wanted to remain as moral and ethical as possible during all times of crisis. David following the ways of the LORD was paramount to him.

Verse twelve

David did not want to become the person that his enemies wanted him to be. When a king was merciful and benevolent, the nobles of the kingdom would despise him. The nobles did not want to help the people. Instead, the nobles wanted to exploit the people. That cannot happen when the King is of high moral character. David refused to become a king that allowed the exploitation of his people by anyone.

Verse thirteen

David believed that if he survived his enemy's attacks, it was due to his faith in the LORD and his prayers. Faith pushed David to continue fighting for the LORD.

Verse fourteen

The conclusion to this Psalm is that we have to put our love and trust in the LORD.

This verse is one of encouragement even if the results are not seen immediately.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

